

TENSILE CREEP BEHAVIOR OF CARBON NANOTUBE REINFORCED EPOXY

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ABSTRACT

The primary objective of this investigation is to characterize the tensile creep behavior of coupon-type specimens consisting of a bisphenol A epoxy resin, amine curative, several processing aids, and as-received arc-derived single-wall carbon nanotube soot material in concentrations of up to 3% by weight. The processing aids consisted of diluent, surfactant, and air-release agent. Also characterized were the degree of nanotube dispersion, the glass transition temperature (T_g), and the coefficient of thermal expansion of the materials. Creep strain data obtained at temperatures below the T_g of the materials were used to construct master creep compliance curves based on the time-temperature superposition principle. A three-parameter Findlay-type creep law was fitted to each creep compliance curve. The addition of nanotube material reduced the creep compliance and increased the T_g relative to the case of epoxy resin containing only the processing aids. However, the processing aids used in this investigation significantly decreased the T_g and increased the creep compliance relative to the neat epoxy resin. The net effects of adding processing aids and nanotube material to the epoxy resin are an increase in creep compliance over the range of temperatures and times investigated, a decrease of T_g , and a negligible change in coefficient of thermal expansion.

KEYWORDS

Nanotube, epoxy, creep, glass transition, thermal expansion

INTRODUCTION

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs), consisting of layers of strongly bonded sheets of carbon atoms arranged into single- or multi-wall cylinders, represent a potentially unique type of functional filler for high performance polymeric resin systems. CNTs can be used to tailor a wide range of material properties such as electrical resistance, coefficient of thermal expansion, thermal conductivity, modulus of elasticity, strength, glass transition temperature, and creep behavior, to name a few [1,2]. On account of their small size (one to several dozen nanometers) and high aspect ratio (at least one thousand), CNTs can have dramatic effects on certain properties of the host resin system with smaller volume fractions than would be the case with traditional filler materials such as carbon black and carbon whiskers [3]. The advantage of lower volume fractions of fillers can be measured in terms of improved processability, better surface finish, and higher ductility of the composite material. The high current cost of CNTs (US\$100 to \$1600/g, depending on the level of purity) is a detriment to the widespread use of the material as filler in polymers, although the material cost is expected to decrease as manufacturing technology matures. In parallel with a concerted effort to reduce the cost of CNTs, there are numerous exploratory investigations underway to assess the potential advances in material properties obtainable by adding CNTs to polymeric materials. To-date, the most compelling results have concerned the electrical properties of polymers [3–5]. Regarding the impact of CNTs on the structural performance of polymers, the results published to-date vary widely and demonstrate much dependence on the particular CNT, polymer, and processing steps used to make the composites as well as the concentration of CNTs in the composite. Some investigators

have reported increases in the elastic modulus and/or strength of polymer composites containing as little as 0.1% by weight CNTs, with the increase becoming more marked at temperatures above the glass transition temperature of the neat polymeric matrix material [5-10]. Shaffer and Windle [6] and Jin et al. [9] observed slight increases of the glass transition temperature of CNT/polymer composites with increasing CNT content. Such improvement in the elevated temperature characteristics of CNT/polymer composites portends possible improvements in the creep resistance of the composites as well.

The primary objective of the investigation reported in this paper is to evaluate the tensile creep compliance of coupon-type CNT/epoxy composites containing as-processed, single-wall CNT soot material in concentrations of up to 3 percent by weight (wt%). The creep behavior of the CNT/epoxy coupons were compared on the basis of tensile compliance master curves constructed using the time-temperature superposition principal. The degree of dispersion of the CNT material in the resin was evaluated with a scanning electron microscope (SEM). The glass transition temperature (T_g) and coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) of the materials were evaluated with a dilatometer.

SPECIMEN PREPARATION

The resin system utilized throughout this study was a mixture of a bisphenol-A epoxy resin, Epon 9405 (Resolution Performance Products, Houston, TX), and a modified, non-MDA, aromatic amine curative, Ancamine 9470 (Air Products & Chemicals, Allentown, PA), selected for its low room-temperature viscosity and long pot life. To compensate for the increase in viscosity caused by the introduction of CNT material to the uncured epoxy mixture, Epodil 749 (Air Products & Chemicals), a difunctional reactive diluent based on neopentyl glycol, was added to the Epon 9405 resin in a weight ratio of 25 parts per 75 parts of epoxy. Curative was added to this mixture in a weight ratio of 41.54 parts per hundred of diluted resin. The epoxy resin, curative, and diluent formed the “resin mixture” for the purpose of calculating the amount of remaining additives in the mixture.

To help eliminate voids in the specimens, BYK-A 501, a silicone-free polymer air release agent (BYK-Chemie, Wallingford, CT), was added in a 0.5 wt% concentration to the resin mixture. The CNT soot material, made by the arc discharge method by Carboxol (Lexington, KY), contained 50-70% single wall CNTs with the remainder being nano-sized particles of other forms of carbon and residual catalyst (Ni and Y). The single-wall CNTs are individually 1-2 nm in diameter and appear naturally in bundles having a mean diameter of ~15 nm [11]. CNT soot material was added to the resin mixture in 1, 2, and 3 wt% concentrations, corresponding to approximately 0.5, 1, and 1.5% CNTs, respectively. A nonionic surfactant — polyoxyethylene 8 lauryl ether ($C_{28}H_{58}O_9$, Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO) — was added to the resin mixture in a 0.76 wt% concentration to help disentangle the naturally agglomerated CNT bundles. Disentanglement and dispersion of the CNT bundles was facilitated by the vigorous agitation of the liquid CNT/epoxy mixture with a 900 W ultrasonic horn. The agitation procedure consisted of six repetitions of 1-min sonication followed by 1-min. cooling in an ice bath. For comparison purposes, two benchmark specimens were made with no CNT soot material. One benchmark specimen, denoted “neat epoxy,” contained only epoxy and curative in a weight ratio of 100 parts epoxy to 37 parts curative. The other benchmark specimen, denoted “0-wt% material,” contained neat epoxy plus the processing aids used in the CNT/epoxy composite (diluent, surfactant, and air release agent). The purpose of the 0-wt% CNT material was to allow isolation of the effects of CNT concentration on the thermomechanical parameters of interest.

Following sonication, the liquid resin was placed into the respective molds for making creep and dilatometer specimens. The uncured creep specimens were degassed under vacuum for 30 minutes in the mold to minimize voids, whereas it was not necessary to degas the dilatometer specimens. All materials were cured for 16 hr at 121°C. Upon de-molding, creep specimens were machined to a final size of 140×15×1.5 mm and then aged in a convection oven. The neat epoxy specimen was aged for 400 hr at

107°C while the other specimens were aged for 260–600 hr at 80°C. The selected aging temperatures were approximately 15°C below the T_g values of the respective specimens. The dilatometer specimens were machined to a final size of 13×9.5×4 mm and were not aged prior to testing.

TESTING

A high temperature epoxy adhesive, M-Bond AE-10 (Measurements Group, Raleigh NC), was used to affix electrical resistance strain gages in the longitudinal orientation on the front and back of the creep specimens. The adhesive was cured for 2 hr at 50°C for at least 6 hr at room temperature, in accordance with the product specifications. To minimize creep in the adhesive during a creep test, the gaged specimens were post cured for 24 hr at 80°C or at the highest temperature of the creep testing sequence when testing above 80°C. Momentary creep tests were carried out at temperatures between 40°C and T_g -15°C using dead weights linked to the specimen through a lever-arm. For a given test, applied stress was held constant at a value between roughly 6 and 7 MPa. The time-temperature superposition principle was utilized to construct a master creep compliance curve for each specimen at a reference temperature of 40°C and a three-parameter Findlay-type creep law for the compliance, D , was fit to the master curves according to eq. (1):

$$D = D_0 + D_1 t^n \quad (1)$$

where D_0 is the instantaneous (elastic) compliance (GPa^{-1}), D_1 is the pre-exponential constant ($\text{s}^{-n} \cdot \text{GPa}^{-1}$), t is the time (s), and n is the time exponent [12].

Fracture surfaces on small pieces of material taken from representative sections of the creep specimens were imaged in the SEM to qualitatively evaluate the dispersion of CNT bundles. The SEM specimens were made conductive by the vapor deposition of an approximately 5-nm-thick gold layer. Dilatometer measurements were made along the 13-mm side of the specimens over a -150 to 150°C temperature range. The T_g values were determined graphically as the intersection of the tangents the roughly bilinear strain versus temperature plots. The CTE was evaluated by fitting a straight line to the strain versus temperature data over the -50 to 25°C range.

RESULTS

SEM photomicrographs of cross sections of creep specimens containing CNTs are shown in Figs. 1-3. Rope-like bundles of CNTs appear as light colored strands on the dark background. Considering the 5-nm gold coating on the surface of the specimens, the diameters of the bundles observed in this investigation are consistent with published data [11]. Based on these images and others not included here, it was concluded that the CNT bundles in the 1- and 2-wt% cases were well distributed throughout the imaged regions of the specimens. In the 3-wt% specimen, however, differences in bundle density could be seen in different regions of the cross-section, as shown in Fig. 3. It is noteworthy that the viscosity of the 3 wt% case was significantly higher than in the 1 and 2 wt% cases, which could have hindered a thorough mixing of the CNT material in the liquid resin during ultrasonic agitation.

The dilatometer results, summarized in Table 1, indicate rather insignificant changes in the CTE with respect to processing additives and concentration of CNT soot material. Additional results not included here suggest a specimen-to-specimen scatter in CTE of approximately $\pm 1 \mu\epsilon/\text{C}$. The T_g results, on the other hand, showed a significant dependence on the composition of the specimens. In particular, the addition of diluent and surfactant decreased the T_g by 32°C, whereas adding CNT soot material in any concentration between 1 and 3 wt% increased the T_g by 6 to 8°C relative to the 0-wt% material. The

experimental accuracy in the T_g measurements is considered to be $\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. These results would suggest that a manufacturing process allowing the introduction of CNT material to the resin without the use of diluent and surfactant would be a preferred processing method to avoid the loss of T_g associated with the use of these materials and to realize the gain in T_g associated with the addition of CNT material. Based on the T_g results in Table 1, the upper temperature limit for momentary creep tests was selected as 110°C for the neat epoxy material and either 70 or 80°C for all the other materials.

Figure 1. SEM photomicrographs of cross-section of Specimen 3-B with 1-wt% CNT material.

Figure 2. SEM photomicrographs of cross-section of Specimen 3-C with 2-wt% CNT material.

Figure 3. SEM photomicrographs of cross-section of Specimen 3-D with 3-wt% CNT material.

Table 1. CTE and T_g results.

Batch Designation	CNT Soot Concentration	CTE ($\mu\epsilon/^\circ\text{C}$)	T_g ($^\circ\text{C}$)
2-H	Neat Epoxy	48	126
3-A	0-wt%	50	94
3-B	1-wt%	51	100
3-C	2-wt%	50	100
3-D	3-wt%	49	102

Master creep compliance curves and the best-fit three-parameter creep equations, $D(t)$, for the neat epoxy and 0-wt% specimens are shown in Fig. 4. Values of the time independent (elastic) term of the creep compliance equation, D_0 , and the value of creep compliance at 10^7 s are listed in Table 2 for direct comparisons. The elastic compliance of the 0-wt% specimen is nearly 7% higher than that of the neat epoxy specimen. At 10^7 sec, D for the 0-wt% specimen is 58% greater than D for the neat epoxy specimen. Thus, the processing additives used to help disperse the CNT ropes in the resin significantly increased the tendency for creep, particularly at longer equivalent times on the master compliance curve.

Figure 4. Comparison of 40°C master creep compliance curves for neat epoxy and 0-wt% specimens.

Table 2. Creep compliance values at $t = 0$ and 10^7 s.

Specimen Designation	CNT Soot Concentration	Elastic Compliance, D_0 (GPa^{-1})	Creep Compliance at $t = 10^7$ s, D (GPa^{-1})
2-H2	Neat Epoxy	0.282	0.311
3-A2	0 wt%	0.301	0.490
3-B	1 wt%	0.294	0.432
3-C	2 wt%	0.299	0.412
3-D	3 wt%	0.286	0.406

In Fig. 5, the master creep compliance curves and 3-parameter creep equations for the 0- through 3-wt% specimens are compared. This comparison illustrates the effect of CNT concentration without

consideration of the effects of the processing additives used to help disperse the CNT material. It can be seen that the creep compliance decreases with increasing concentrations of CNT material. Most of the reduction in compliance occurs with a CNT soot concentration of 1 wt%, with diminishing returns for higher concentrations. The elastic compliance is reduced by 2 to 5% as the CNT material concentration increases from 1 to 3 wt% (Table 2). Differences in D among specimens with 1 to 3 wt% CNT material practically vanish at longer times. However, the difference in D between the 0-wt% specimen and the general grouping of three specimens with CNTs slightly widens at longer times. For example, at 10^7 s, the average value of D for the specimen containing CNTs (0.417 GPa^{-1}) is 15% less than the corresponding value of D in the 0-wt% specimen (Table 2). As CNT content increases, it is also noted that the pre-exponent term in D decreases while the time exponent increases. This result implies that the compliance curves for the materials with CNTs have greater upward curvature and, therefore, a more rapid time-rate of increase in creep rate in comparison to the 0-wt% material. More testing is needed to ascertain if the reduction in long-term D observed with added CNT reinforcement remains true at even longer equivalent times on the master creep compliance curve.

Figure 5. Comparison of 40°C master creep compliance curves for 0-, 1-, 2-, and 3-wt% specimens.

In comparing the elastic compliance of the neat epoxy specimen to the average elastic compliance for the specimens reinforced with CNT material (0.282 and 0.293 GPa^{-1} , respectively), it can be seen that the difference is insignificant. At 10^7 s, the compliances for the neat epoxy and the average of three CNT specimens tested are 0.311 and 0.417 GPa^{-1} , respectively, representing a 34% increase in creep compliance due to the addition of processing additives and CNT material to the epoxy.

CONCLUSIONS

The 6-minute, high-power, ultrasonic mixing procedure developed in this investigation results in a homogeneous distribution of individual rope-shaped bundles of single wall CNTs in concentrations of 1 to 3 wt% in a diluted epoxy resin. The 3-wt% case does not appear as well dispersed as the 1- and 2-wt% cases under the same preparation conditions due to insufficient mixing. The difficulty in mixing is attributed to the higher viscosity of the 3-wt% mixture. The addition of processing aids (diluent, surfactant, and air release agent) and CNT material to the epoxy resin did not affect the CTE of the

material significantly. The addition of the processing aids decreased the T_g by 32°C, whereas adding CNT material in any concentration between 1 and 3 wt% increased the T_g by 6–8°C relative to the material with only processing aids added (0-wt% material). Thus, there was an overall reduction of T_g when processing aids and CNT material were added to the neat epoxy resin. Similarly, the addition of the processing aids increased the creep compliance of the epoxy significantly. Adding CNTs to the epoxy with processing aids decreased the creep compliance relative the case of epoxy containing just processing aids, but not sufficiently to overcome the effect of the processing aids. It is therefore concluded that CNTs can reduce creep in epoxy materials, but this potential advantage can be overshadowed by the use of additives meant to improve processability of the liquid mixture. In future research, it is recommended to find an alternative method of preparing specimens that does not require the use of these additives. Other issues that need to be investigated are the effects of impurities in the CNT material and the degree of bonding between the CNTs and the epoxy resin.

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